

Automated scalable Spray coating of SnO₂ for the fabrication of low temperature perovskite solar cells and modules

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In the renewable energy field, the use of hybrid perovskite materials has opened up new directions to fabricate cost effective and highly efficient photovoltaic devices. Despite impressive power conversion efficiency (PCE), exceeding 25.2% ^[1], demonstrated on lab-scale devices (0.1 cm²), scalability and stability of device are still topical issues. In this context, large area deposition procedures and automatized fabrication protocols are required in order to achieve high throughput serial production of modules and panels. Tin oxide (SnO₂) is a low-cost Electron Transport Layer (ETL) that it is commonly deposited by Spin-Coating ^[2,3]. In this work, we demonstrated a first-ever spray coated SnO₂ layer processed at low temperature for the realization of planar direct Perovskite Solar Cells (PSCs) and modules. This demonstrates that this is an effective scalable technique in producing perovskite solar devices. The devices employing sprayed SnO₂ layer achieve an efficiency that is comparable with respect to that obtained using spin-coated one. We report on an efficient low-temperature solution-processed SnO₂ nanoparticles in applications for ETL of PSCs. Using sprayed nano particles of SnO₂ (Np-SnO₂) as ETL, CH₃NH₃PbI₃ based solar device showed a maximum PCE of 16.77% (avg. 15.01%) with respect to 17% (avg.15.5%) of spin coated Np-SnO₂. Furthermore, long-term stability of devices has not worsened for the sprayed SnO₂. Unencapsulated cells based on sprayed SnO₂ stored in 25°C and 50% relative humidity showed shelf life stability by retaining 85% of the initial PCE value after more than 1000 hours. Similar behaviour was observed for the PCE of the spin coated SnO₂ cells. Moreover, we demonstrated the feasibility of fabrication of the modules with 15cm² active area which reached 9.37% of PCE from uniform spray deposited SnO₂ film on large area 20×20 cm². Additionally, by using Np-SnO₂ we demonstrated the possibility of decreasing PSC fabrication temperature down to 100°C, that would be very attractive for flexible PSCs. This provides a viable route to easily combine low-cost, stability and high efficiency for the next generation perovskite photovoltaic devices.

Abstract image

1. Introduction

Organometal halide perovskites have unique optoelectronic properties that justify their use as absorbing material in the new generation solar technology. The materials used, as well as the solution-based printing deposition methods of these materials, are not expensive. Additionally, the high absorption coefficient and the direct bandgap of these materials makes possible full absorption of visible light, only with few hundreds nanometre of perovskite film ($< 500 \text{ nm}$)^[4]. Combining these features, Perovskite Solar Cells (PSCs) provides fabrication feasibility of low cost, high-performance, thin, lightweight and flexible solar modules.

In the early years of research on perovskite photovoltaics, the big challenge was the demonstration of high efficiency on devices as large as a coin. At present, researchers have demonstrated fabrication of perovskite solar modules (PSMs) using blade coating printing technique connecting the cells in series (Z connection) ^[5], with a yield of about 15.6% on an active area of 12.0 cm^2 and an outstanding shelf stability maintaining 90% power conversion efficiency after 3600 h aging ^[6]. To realize high efficiency module, it is necessary to make the manufacturing of each layer scalable, avoiding the

efficiency drop in the upscaling step. In the case of planar PSCs with direct n-i-p configuration, the electron transporting layers (ETLs) play crucial role for the device performances. It must assure large interfacial surface, long electron diffusion length, and excellent perovskite infiltration ^[7]. To date, the efficient perovskite cells mainly use a TiO₂ mesoporous ETLs, and large-area scalable metal oxide scaffold fabricated by spray coating was demonstrated ^[8] whose main drawback is that it needs high-temperature annealing procedure (>450 °C) which severely limits its application in commercial-size and flexible devices ^[9]. In contrast, SnO₂ exhibits several distinct advantages: low-temperature solution fabrication (<180 °C), high electron mobility and ease of adapting its electro-optical properties by tuning its composition and morphology^[3, 10]. Recently, high-efficiency based SnO₂ PSCs with PCE up to 23.3% are reported ^[11], which is very close to the highest PCE of 25.2% obtained for PSCs ^[1].

SnO₂ ETLs in n-i-p planar perovskite solar cells is commonly deposited by spin-coating technique^[2, 12, 13] which is not a scalable deposition technique ^[14]. In order to move to large area process diverse technique such as electrodeposition^[15], Atomic Layer Deposition (ALD) ^[16], Chemical Bath Deposition (CBD) ^[17], Slot-die ^[18] or high temperature spray pyrolysis^[19] have been used by scientific community to deposit SnO₂.

In contrast to the techniques mentioned above, which need substrates with flat surface, spray-coating is very advantageous large area deposition technique adaptable with conformable substrate, able to speed up perovskite modules fabrication by pushing the perovskite solar devices towards the market. With this coating technique, SnO₂ film formation is obtained by depositing small droplets of material on the substrate instead of a wet film deposition typical of the spin, blade or other screen deposition^[20]. The drying dynamics of the landed droplets in spray coating is the most critical step to form a film of desired quality. The drying time is a function of droplet size, solvent boiling point, substrate temperature, and conditions of the surrounding air^[21]. Up to now, few specific studies have been focused the attention on spray coating of SnO₂ for the fabrication of PSCs. Recently Mahmood

et al. ^[22] (using Electrospray at 170°C) demonstrated well-connected and highly porous SnO₂ nanosheets ETLs in the perovskite solar cells, by reaching maximum PCE 15.69%. They have shown charge collection efficiency and light harvesting improvements of the electrospray-based PSCs compared to the conventional hydrothermal technique, due to wide band gap energy, better perovskite infiltration and high transparency of the electrospray SnO₂ nanosheets. Despite the promising result reported by using electrospray coating technique, its application to large area or flexible devices has not been demonstrated probably due to deposition temperature (temperature limit~150 °C for PET/ITO ^[23]) as well as to stability and device performance.

In this paper we introduced a low temperature solution-processed Automated Spray Coating (ASC) technique for the deposition of SnO₂ as ETLs to yield highly efficient perovskite solar cells with PCE_{max} =16.77%, the firstly ever reported for spray SnO₂ nanoparticles-based perovskite solar cells to date. The ASC (see **Figure 1**) method of SnO₂ reported in this paper overcomes the coating size limitation of the existing stationary spray, single-pass spray, manual airbrush and spin-coating methods. ASC as well as other spray techniques it is not affected by the roughness of the substrate, which is a disadvantage of other processed solution techniques. In contrast with the spin-coating method there is a low material waste, since the holder of the substrate is large, and the spray technique allows covering the whole area in terms of the second. These advantages of ASC of ETLs respect to other deposition technique directed us to using ASC SnO₂ for fabrication of uniform electron transport film on large area substrate. Finally, ASC SnO₂ employed for fabrication of perovskite solar modules is firstly proven, by achieving a PCE of 9.37% on 15 cm² of active area.

2. Results and discussion

2.1 Sprayed ETLs optimization for PSCs

In the current work, the SnO₂ films were deposited on FTO glass substrates using a professional automated spray coating that is schematically illustrated in **Figure 1**.

The drying dynamics of the landed droplets is the most critical step to form a sprayed film with desired quality. The smaller are the drops that reach the surface, the better is the growth of the film. Notably, SnO₂ film characteristics such as roughness and transmittance were also influenced by droplet size and spray patterns coverage. The droplet size is a function of liquid properties, solution flow rate and spraying pressure parameters. The theoretical coverage of spray patterns is influenced by spray angle and the distance from the nozzle orifice. The effective spray angle varies with aperture of nozzle and liquid viscosity.

As comparison of pre-synthesized Np-SnO₂ dispersed in water, we studied the ASC of a SnO₂ ETL prepared with a sol-gel approach starting from chlorinated precursors dissolved in alcoholic solvent. This approach was commonly used since Ke et al.^[24] in 2015 demonstrated the possibility to obtain high performance planar PSCs with a low-T approach ($T < 180^{\circ}\text{C}$).^[12, 25] In addition the optimization steps leading the stoichiometric SnO₂ formation was deeply investigated from our group by using HR-XPS analysis.^[26]

Place of Figure 1 First of all, we studied the influence of the substrate temperature on the film morphology and transparency of ETLs layer. Other relevant parameters, such as the flow rate pressure and the spray distance, which have a direct effect on the size of the individual spray drops and droplet force impacting on the substrate surface, are kept fixed at this stage.

Spray coating of ETLs under study were done in ambient air with the substrate heated at different temperatures (25, 40, 60, 80 and 120 °C). Standard spin coating deposition (performed at room

temperature) was also considered for comparison. As reported in **Figure 2**, the substrate temperature during the ASC ETL deposition has a strong influence in the film homogeneity. This step is fundamental to have an ETL pinholes-free formation required for the high device performances. When the substrate temperature is higher than 40°C, the drying of the sprayed droplets is faster, leading to a too rough film's surface (see **Figure 2c**). In order to produce a smooth film, the conditions that lie in the narrow window between the dry regime and the wet regime need to be found ^[27]. The correct choice of the solvents and the fine-tuning of the substrate temperature lead to the optimum conditions. For Solgel-SnO₂ in ethanol the best deposition temperature was found to be 25 °C, while for Np-SnO₂ in water at 40°C we obtained less pinholes surface, as shown in the microscope images reported **Figure 2a-b**.

In the optimal conditions, the low substrate temperatures allowed the solvent to reach the substrate surface with a consequent flattening of the SnO₂ surface leading to a superior uniformity of the film as observed by the confocal micrographs. Furthermore, we show that the control on the spray regime has a strong effect on the power conversion efficiency: the SnO₂ film morphology obtained for the deposition at lower temperature led PSCs performance to be better compared to that of the PSCs produced with higher temperatures, (**Figure 2d**).

Place of Figure 2 Beside the deposition temperature, for film quality improvement of sprayed SnO₂ it is essential to consider other spray coating parameters, such as: gas pressure, nozzle aperture, spray deposition velocity, flow rate solution, spray distance and spray cycle times.

Accordingly, our study was carried on finding the optimum combination of spray deposition parameters that allowed to reach proper morphology of the film in terms of roughness and transparency. To serve this purpose we fixed flow rate and distance of spray nozzle to the substrate at 40 mL/min, and 9 cm respectively. Viscosity of our spray solution was kept in a constant rate (see experimental section). Whereas, nitrogen gas pressure was changed from 1 to 2 bar and apertures of nozzle was varied from 50µm to 60µm.

When spraying both nanoparticles and solgel precursor solutions of SnO₂, the optical transparency in the visible range increases increasing the nitrogen pressure. Thus, spray coated SnO₂ transmittance approaches the one observed for the standard spin coated SnO₂ one, which is beneficial for the light harvesting from the perovskite film (see **Figure S1**). This phenomenon is probably related to the decreasing of the spray's droplet size that has an inverse-relationship with increasing spraying pressure ^[28] .

The optimum deposition parameters were three cycle spray at room temperature with aperture of nozzle 50 μm, nitrogen pressure of 2bar and deposition velocity of 200mm/s (S_o) for Solgel and one cycle spray with nozzle aperture of 60 μm, nitrogen pressure of 1.5bar and deposition velocity of 600mm/s at 40°C (N_o) for nanoparticles.

In **Figure 3a** we show that the transmittance spectra of the optimised sprayed SnO₂ films is similar to that obtained with spin coated samples. Moreover, proper drop density, and a well-improved surface coverage (see microscope images of **Figure 3b**) is found, which is highly beneficial to blocking holes and consequently to prevent short-circuits between FTO glass substrate and perovskite absorber. Top view SEM images and Atomic Force Micrograph (AFM) of only SnO₂ films on FTO substrate are reported in **Figure 3c and d**. Here it is possible to notice that in case of SnO₂ nanoparticles films the spray coated samples are comparable with the spin coated ones both in morphology and in roughness, while in case of SnO₂ sol gel films a slightly different morphology and a relatively higher roughness is obtained. This could explain the performances in terms of efficiency and reproducibility achieved with spray coated SnO₂ sol gel films.

Place of Figure 3

It is important to remark that not only the optical and electrical properties are important in defining the quality of the ESL in n-i-p perovskite solar cells, but also its influence on the morphology of the

perovskite film growth on top, as the SnO₂ here is also the substrate for the perovskite growth. Vast literature has been devoted to the understanding of the effect of the perovskite film quality on the performances on solar cells, with the morphology being one of the most impacting properties [29]. Therefore, we conducted SEM investigation to state if the perovskite growth is affected by the different deposition technique of the substrate. The SEM images of perovskite layer on automated spray deposited SnO₂ and on spin coated SnO₂ are shown in **Figure 4**. In all cases, the morphology is constituted by the classical dense packing of spherical grains with an equivalent diameter above 200 nm. Interestingly, it appears that the deposition technique of SnO₂ is minimally affecting the perovskite growth. Independently from deposition techniques, a small difference is found when comparing the perovskite growth from the nanoparticle's solution and from the sol-gel precursor. Perovskite film with larger grains and a more homogeneous surface appears to be that of the nanoparticle. However, the key point is that the surface morphology of the perovskite crystals grown over spin and spray coated SnO₂ are not significantly different.

Place of Figure 4

Figure 5 reports the distribution of the photovoltaic parameters (PCE, J_{SC}, FF and V_{OC}) for PSCs based on Np-SnO₂ and Solgel-SnO₂ deposited by ASC and spin coating techniques. Notably, for both deposition techniques, the PSCs based on Np-SnO₂ show an enhancement of FF and of J_{SC} with respect to the ones with Solgel-SnO₂. The SnO₂ film morphology obtained for the deposition Solgel and Nanoparticles via spray coating led to obtain PSCs performance comparable with the PSCs with SnO₂ produced with spin coated method. More in detail, the best PCE reached 16.7% for Np-SnO₂ and 15.4% for Solgel when both materials have been spray-coated. Furthermore, it is noteworthy that the average PCE of sprayed ETLs Solgel-SnO₂ and Np-SnO₂ are 89% and 94% of spin coated samples respectively (see **Figure 5**). J-V curve of best samples and hysteresis index calculated for each type of tin oxide film are reported in **Figure S2**. Hysteresis behaviour presents in J-V curves might be due to slow transient capacitive current, dynamic trapping and de-trapping processes of charge carriers,

and ion migration or ferroelectric polarization inside the device [20, 21] which is common in planar structure with $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ perovskite [2, 17, 30].

Place of Figure 5

To gain a deeper understanding of the effect of deposition technique and the precursor of SnO_2 on the PSCs performance, electro-optical characterizations and transient measurements are carried out on PSCs. From IPCE curves shown in **Figure 6** the photogenerated current of Np-based cells is higher than those of Solgel at wavelength of 300-500nm. In this high photon energy region, the electron-hole pair are generated close to SnO_2 layer and the efficiency of the electron extraction from SnO_2 is dominant^[31]. Therefore, Np- SnO_2 might provide a better charge extraction, in agreement with the higher efficiency obtained from the devices. At longer wavelengths (ranging from 600 to 800 nm), the most important contributions are the light harvesting from the perovskite and the transport of the charges toward the contacts. Here, minor differences are found between the four-condition investigated. Overall, the IPCE spectra confirmed that Np- SnO_2 based device exhibited a higher photogenerated current (especially at low wavelengths), and this explains the improvements of Np- SnO_2 based cells respect to Solgel-based cells. The resulting higher integrated photocurrent obtained with the nanoparticles is in accordance J_{sc} measured under Sun Simulator.

Together with photo charge generation and transport, the recombination paths ultimately define the efficiency of the solar cells. To gain insight into the recombination in a full device the transient photovoltage (TPV) technique is particularly suited. In this technique, a light pulse is applied, generating a photovoltage. The cell is kept at open circuit, therefore the subsequent fall in V_{oc} must be attributed to the internal recombinations. Notably, this technique is well suited to probe the dynamics of the space charge formed at the selective contacts^[32]. Photovoltage decay can be attributed to charge trapping, recombination processes and transporting of charges^[33]. The drop in potential depends on the recombination phenomena at two different interfaces ETL/Perovskite and Perovskite/HTL and it also depends on how the accumulated charges at the different interfaces recombine. In addition, the

recombination in perovskite layer can be radiative and not radiative, with different kinetics. When these processes present different time scales, more complex transients of a single exponential can be obtained. [32, 34] Interestingly the Solgel-SnO₂ based devices reach discharged condition in less than 1 milliseconds that is lower than the one obtained for the Np-SnO₂ cells (<10ms) (see **Figure 7**). This measure explains that the higher FF of the cells based on Np-SnO₂ respect to Solgel based cells (see **Figure 5**) is due to decrease of the recombination process [35].

Place of Figure 6

Place of Figure 7

Device stability is a crucial matter for industrialization of PSCs. **Figure 8** shows the normalized long-term stability test, for spin and spray coated devices with different ETLs. The starting photovoltaic parameters of each device and the non-normalized graph are reported in **Figure S3**. Shelf life test was carried out on unencapsulated cells stored under ambient conditions where temperature and relative humidity were about 25 °C and 40% respectively. All devices demonstrate similar stability, where the initial PCE is retained over 85% after 1000 h of storage. The slight improved ambient cells stability of spray coated SnO₂ devices can be ascribed to higher roughness of SnO₂ respect to spin SnO₂ which allows the complete pore filling with perovskite absorber preventing the decomposition of perovskite [19, 36].

Place of Figure 8

2.2 Automated sprayed ETL for perovskite solar modules

The results of the PSCs comparison (are shown **Figure 5**) confirm that ETL film based on SnO₂ nanoparticles are less sensitive to deposition technique, obtaining only a drop of 6% of efficiency against 12% in the case of Solgel. To test the effectiveness of our proposed low temperature ETL automated spray coating approach, we fabricated Perovskite Solar Modules (PSMs). We chose to use

Np-SnO₂ as they were the best ETL in terms of performance to exploit both scale-up potentiality of the developed ASC and the low temperature processing as the Np-SnO₂ have to be annealed at 100°C. In the view of scaling up, it is important to highlight that the lower temperature processing helps in minimising the mechanical stress of the large glass substrate. In order to evaluate homogeneity of the large area deposited films, the transmittance spectrum at different positions of substrate and the optical microscope images have been characterized (see **Figure S4b** and **Figure S4c** respectively). The microscope images and transmittance spectra measured in nine different location of 10 x 10 cm² of the substrate coincide, demonstrating the homogeneity of the process in the whole sprayed area.

To realize the mini modules, the spray deposition was firstly accomplished on a large-area laser patterned substrate (20× 20 cm²). Secondly, the substrate was divided into 5× 5 cm² pieces to finalize the fabrication of the four perovskite solar mini modules (PSMs). Each mini module is fabricated on a 25 cm² substrate area, consisting of eight series connected PSCs (active area 1.84 cm²), with an overall active area of 15 cm². The module aperture ratio (AR), i.e., the ratio between the active area and the aperture area, is approximately 87% (see the schematic representation of mini module layout reported in **Figure 9**)

Place of Figure 9

The photovoltaic performance parameters of the perovskite mini modules are reported in **Table 1**, the PCE was calculated measuring PSMs that are composed of 8 cells connected in series with the formula reported in supporting info **Equation S1** ^[37]. The corresponding stabilized efficiency and J-V curves are shown in **Figure 10** and **Figure S4** respectively.

The sprayed Np-SnO₂ show average PCE (PCE_{avg}) equal to 8.97%±0.40 obtained from a batch of three mini modules. The achieved PCE_{avg} of spray-based modules is 94% of PCE_{avg} of spin coated one. Indeed, the main drop of PCE is linked to the decrease in V_{OC} (-9%) and the slight reduction of I_{SC} (-3.9%).

This demonstrates for the first time the possibility of using spray coating technique to fabricate large area modules.

Place of Figure 103. Conclusion

The manufacturing process of perovskite solar cells (PSC) is rapidly moving towards the consolidation of deposition processes that can be extended to large areas, compatible with all types of surfaces for industrial exploitation. In this work, we introduced the combined concept of automated spray coating at low temperature and the use of SnO₂ nanoparticles that is an effective strategy to extend dimension of PSCs and to realize large area devices and modules. More in detail, the PSC fabricated on a small-area with spray-coated Np-SnO₂ has shown an average power conversion efficiency of 15% (max 16.7%), which is 94% of that obtained for PSC using spin-coated Np-SnO₂ (16.1%). These results were also confirmed on modules, which achieved a PCE of 9.37% using spray-coated Np-SnO₂, against 10.62% obtained by the reference spin coated PSM. Electro-optical characterizations and transient measurements have shown that using Np-SnO₂ instead of conventional Solgel-SnO₂ can improve charge time life at perovskite/ETL interface, in addition, can decrease the overall process temperature. We demonstrated Spray coating of ETLs not affected the stability of PSCs under self-life test (1000h) with devices, which retained more than 85% of the initial PCE value. These results pave the way to realize stabilized planar perovskite solar modules with a versatile, low-cost and industrial assembly line compatible printing technique.

4. Experimental section

4.1. Fabrication of SnO₂ layer using automated spray process

The ETLs composed of SnO₂ nanoparticle or Solgel were directly deposited in air condition with a controlled moisture levels (RH = 40%) on pre-cleaned fluorine-doped tin-oxide (FTO) glass substrates through ACS^[38]. For Np-SnO₂, 10% Tin (IV) oxide nanoparticles in H₂O colloidal

dispersion was used and for Solgel approach the 0.1 M $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in EtOH was used to prepare precursor solution. The precursor solution was placed in a reservoir and it was continuously recirculated through a gear pump (FG204, fluido tech, italy) inside the spray nozzle. The solution was atomized at the tip of the nozzle into an aerosol by applying gas pressure using a nitrogen cylinder. The Flow rate, the path of spray and distance of spray nozzle to the substrate were kept at 40 mL/min, sinusoidal (support info) and 9 cm respectively. The substrate temperature ranges from 25 to 120 °C and nitrogen pressure varies from 1 to 2 bar. Np- SnO_2 and Solgel- SnO_2 were deposited at two different apertures of nozzle (50 μm and 60 μm) by fixing the spraying cycle to 3 times.

4.2. Fabrication of SnO_2 layer using spin coating method

The Np- SnO_2 (10% Tin (IV) oxide nanoparticles in H_2O colloidal solution) was spin coated onto Glass/FTO substrates at 4000 rpm for 45 s, while the Solgel- SnO_2 samples were prepared by spin-coating the 0.1M solution at 2500 rpm for 30 s.

The deposited SnO_2 thin films were annealed in air, Np- SnO_2 at 100 °C for 1 hour and Solgel at 180°C for 3 hours then all ETL films were treated with UV lamp for 15 min before perovskite deposition ^[26].

4.3. Solar cell fabrication

To make the perovskite precursor solution, 717.76 mg mL^{-1} of PbI_2 and 247.56 mg mL^{-1} of $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{I}$ were dissolved in mixed Dimethyl Sulfoxide (DMSO) and N,N-Dimethylformamide (DMF) solvents (1:8 by volume) by stirring for 24h at room temperature. The as-prepared precursor solution was then deposited onto the FTO/ SnO_2 with two steps spin coating, first 1000 rpm for 10 s and then 5000 rpm for 45 s. Just 34 s before the end of the second spin coating step, 0.7 mL of diethyl ether was dropped on the substrates. Subsequently, the perovskite layer was treated with a double step annealing process: 50°C for 2 min and then at 100°C for 10 min. The hole transporting material (HTM) spiro-OMeTAD

in chlorobenzene (CB) (73.5 mg/mL) was employed with additives of lithium bis-(trifluoromethyl sulphonyl)imide in acetonitrile (16.6 μ L, 520 mg/mL), 7.2 μ L of cobalt additive (FK209, 0.25 M in acetonitrile) and 4-tert-butylpyridine (27 μ L) was spin-coated over the perovskite surface at 2000 rpm for 20 s. Finally, the cells were completed by thermal evaporation of Au (80 nm) as the top electrode. The devices were masked with an aperture of 0.1 cm² to describe the active working area.

4.4. Module Fabrication

Fluorine-doped Tin Oxide (FTO)-coated glasses (Pilkington, 8 Ω /□, 20cm x 20cm) is etched with infrared Nd:YVO₄ laser beam to obtain the layout of the eight constituent modules (P1 ablation). The scheme is reported in the Supplementary Information as **Figure S6**.

Regarding the constituent module, the layout was based on 8 series-connected cells with 4.5mm as cell width and with an overall active area of 15 cm² (active area 1.84 cm²). The module aperture ratio (AR), i.e., the ratio between the active area and the aperture area, is approximately 87% (see the schematic representation of mini module layout reported in **Figure 9a**).

After the P1 laser ablation, the patterned substrate is cleaned in an ultrasonic bath, using detergent with de-ionized water, acetone and isopropanol (10 minutes for each step). The etched FTO glass (20cm x 20cm) was used for the SnO₂ deposition of eight mini modules in a single process. Then, the FTO/SnO₂ glass was divided in eight single substrates of 5cm x 5cm. The amount of solution and anti-solvent needed for the perovskite deposition for modules are 350 μ l of perovskite solution and 1.2ml of diethyl ether used for solvent quenching method. Furthermore, 300 μ l of Spiro-OMeTAD was used for HTL deposition. The spin-coating parameters for perovskite and Spiro-OMeTAD were optimized with respect to the same on small area devices.

Furthermore, the P2 ablation is performed in order to remove the device stack on the interconnection areas. The laser parameters are optimized to remove SnO₂/Perovskite/Spiro-OMeTAD stack on

modules with fluence (Φ) equal to 0.115 J/cm^2 . Samples are introduced into a high vacuum chamber (10^{-6} mbar) to thermally evaporate Au back contacts (nominal thickness 100 nm). Finally, P3 ablation are performed using the same laser system and parameters employed in the P2 step, in order to obtain the electrical insulation between the counter-electrodes of adjacent cells.

4.5. Characterization

The morphology of the SnO_2 ETLs and perovskite layers were observed by using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) FE-SEM ZEISS and confocal microscope (Olympus BX51M). AFM topographic measurements were obtained in air by employing a commercial microscope NTEGRA (NT-MDT). In order to obtain a sufficiently large and detectable mechanical deflection, we used ($k=40 \text{ Nm}^{-1}$) silicon tips (NCHV-A, Bruker) with oscillating frequencies in the range between 270 - 400 KHz. The mean square roughness (R_q) has been estimated by averaging the values obtained on four $10.24 \times 10.24 \text{ }\mu\text{m}^2$ images (512×512 pixels) acquired on different regions of the sample (corresponding to about $400 \text{ }\mu\text{m}^2$ of sampled surface). Raw AFM data were treated by using a planar flattening procedures to remove the experimental artifacts due to the piezo-scanners. The film Roughness of SnO_2 was measured also by Dektak Veeco 150 profilometer. The transmission spectra of the ETLs grown on FTO substrate were measured by an UV-vis spectrophotometer (Dymax EC-5000 lamp) in a wavelength range of 300–850 nm at room temperature. The current density vs voltage (J-V) characteristics of the cells were obtained under AM 1.5 G illumination (100 mW/cm^2), which was generated by a class A solar simulator (ABET Sun 2000) equipped with a Keithley 2420 source meter, the j-v scan rate was 33 mV/s . The external quantum efficiency (EQE) spectra and Open Circuit Photovoltage Decay were collected using an optical power density-based measurement system (Arkeo-Cicci research s.r.l.) under the irradiation of 300 W xenon.

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Figure 1. a) Schematic representation of SnO₂ deposition with spray setting parameters b) whole automated spray coating equipment and c) photo of the movable system with two spray heads showing the various components

Figure 2. Confocal microscope images of spray coated SnO₂ at different temperature a) Solgel-SnO₂ and b) Np-SnO₂. c) Roughness of SnO₂ film and d) Power Conversion efficiency of complete solar devices based on SnO₂ spray coated at different temperature

Figure 3. a) Comparison of SnO₂ film Transmittance spin and spray coated with optimum spray setting parameters b) Confocal microscope images of spin and spray coated SnO₂, c) Top view SEM images and d) Atomic Force Micrograph (AFM) of the surface of SnO₂ layer on FTO deposited by ASC and spin coating.

Figure 4. Top view SEM images of Perovskite layer grown up on SnO₂ layer deposited by ASC and spin coating.

Figure 5. Statistics comparison of electrical parameters: Between 36 small-area (0.1 cm²) PSCs based on Solgel-SnO₂ and 32 PSCs based on Np-SnO₂ deposited by ASC and spin coating techniques. The cells were measured under 1 SUN AM 1.5G illumination.

Figure 6. IPCE and integrated current density of PSCs devices based on solgel and Np-SnO₂ deposited by ASC and Spin coater.

Figure 7 :Open Circuit Photovoltage Decay of complete perovskite solar devices.

Figure 8: shelf life of tested PSCs typologies measured under 1 SUN illumination 1.5AM stored under ambient conditions ($RH= 50\%$, $T=25^{\circ}C$).

Figure 9. a) Schematic image of the perovskite solar cell structure and the module interconnections comprising a FTO electrode, $Np-SnO_2$ blocking layer, a perovskite active layer of methylammonium iodide and lead iodide (MAPI), an organic holetransport layer (Spiro-MeOTAD) and a gold (Au) electrode. The P1-P2-P3 patterning steps ^[39] are performed after the patterned layer or layer stack is coated. P1 and P3 disconnect the contacts to separate the subcells, while the P2 scribe is used for the interconnection of neighboring cells b) Image of perovskite solar modules.

<i>Mini module type</i>	<i>PCE_{max}(PCE_{avg}) (%)</i>	<i>V_{oc} (mV)</i>	<i>J_{sc} (mA/cm² strip⁻¹)^a</i>	<i>FF (%)</i>	<i>Active Area (cm²)</i>
Np-SnO ₂ Spin	10.62 (9.50)	7720	15.25	72.2	15
Np-SnO ₂ Spray	9.37 (8.97)	7024	14.60	73.1	15

^a Current density (J_{sc}) of a single strip

Table 1. Electrical parameters of sprayed large-area (15 cm²) PSMs compared with the ones exploiting spin-coated SnO₂. All the devices were measured under 1 sun AM 1.5G illumination.

Figure 10. Stabilized PCE of Perovskite solar modules based on ACS and spin coating SnO₂ with 15 cm² active area